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TABLIX for International Conference on Live Interfaces

Performance Paper

Video of presentation can be found [here](#)

TABLIX

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Introduction

TABLIX is a continuous study of Digital Technology¹ through the language of the Tabla² aimed to develop and support synergistic musical expression in relationship to the artistic process, performance technique & ergonomics of the Tabla musician (Tabla-ji / Tabla-chee / Tabla-ist / Tabla-wala).

TABLIX was initiated with a creative desire to digitally pitch shift the Purra. Tuning the Purra or Dayan (treble drum of the Tabla) to the tonic of the musical piece one is playing or the musician(s) they are accompanying is the first step in the artistic process of conversing musically with the Tabla.

In its current form, TABLIX is a digital Tabla interface. An acoustic Tabla augmented with software and hardware enabling the Tablaji to digitally pitch shift the Purra to any desirable monophonic or polyphonic group of notes (up to 4 voices) in real time via MIDI³ protocol. Connecting and conversing with MIDI in this manner opens up the Tabla and musician through their artform to ideate, compose, edit, perform, explore, and collaborate with MIDI based artists and processes in unique and evolving ways.

Tabla background

Providing a thorough legacy of the Tabla and its language would be far beyond the scope of this paper and my ability to do so. However, I will share some important and relevant features of the Tabla and my relationship with them to provide context for TABLIX.

¹ Origin: early 17th century from Greek *tekhnologia* 'systematic treatment' from *tekhne* 'art, craft' + *logia* 'study of'. Thus my interpretation of digital technology is the study of the digital artform

² Sadanand Naimpalli, *Theory and Practice of Tabla*. Popular Prakashan, 2006, p.8.

³ MIDI is the acronym for Musical Instrument Digital Interface <https://www.midi.org/>, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIDI>

Tabla History & Characteristics

There are many theories in regards to how the Tabla was invented. The most common being that the Tabla was developed by Amir Khusro Ji approximately 250 years ago⁴, evolving from splitting the Pakhawaj; a two headed barrel shaped drum in half. At this time, the primary vocal style of music was transforming from Dhrupad, for which Pakhawaj was used; to Khayaal, for which the Tabla was developed. The Tabla was a new instrument, however the language, concept, technique, rhythmic patterns and oral tradition of the Pakhawaj was utilized and modified to explore it.

The Tabla is a melodic percussion instrument comprised of two, separate, vertically facing drums; a Purra which produces treble sounds and a Duggi which creates the bassier sounds. (*ICLI Video Reference - 5:03*). The Pakhawaj also has a bass and treble side but as opposite faces of a horizontally played barrel drum.

Tabla Construction⁵

The body of the Purra is made from a tapered cylindrical piece of wood approximately 5-6" in diameter at the top, wider at the bottom and approximately 12" high. The wooden body is usually hollowed out around two-thirds of it's length; leaving an approximately 4" solid enclosed base and open face with an upper rim of about ½" thick.

The enclosed body of the Duggi is constructed as a spherical looking pot with a shell thickness of approximately 1/16", face diameter opening of 9-10", and approximate height of 12". The Duggi body was initially made from clay but these days steel, brass, or copper are the more common materials used for manufacturing.

Both the Duggi and Purra faces are covered with a Pudi⁶; a three layered goat skin which is stitched together with a braided rim known as the Gajara. The main layer of Pudi (drum skin) is known as the Maidan on which a Shyahi is applied. The Pudi is placed over the face of the Duggi or Purra and fastened to the body of the respective shells by a strap made from goat intestines known as Badri. The Badri fastens the Pudi via the Gajara to the drum body in a lacing type pattern that continues in a repeated circumferential manner creating stretch and tension of the Pudi over the face of the body.

⁴ Eric Phinney, *TABLA: Drums of North India* <https://www.bsmny.org/instrument-discovery/tabla/#:~:text=Whether%20that%20is%20true%20or,style%20of%20music%20called%20Khayaal.>

⁵ David Courtney, *Tabla Making in the Deccan* <http://chandrakantha.com/tablasite/articles/tblamkng.htm>

⁶ David Courtney, *The Tabla Pudi* <https://chandrakantha.com/tablasite/articles/pudi.htm>

The Shyahi⁷ is a black circular spot made from iron filings, rice paste, and ink. The particular ingredients of the Shyahi compound varies with each Tabla maker. The Shyahi is systematically applied in layers while wet to achieve desired pitch, sound, and tonal qualities for both the Purra and Duggi respectively. The finished Shyahi paste dries to a cement-like consistency and naturally forms cracks creating small grains & particles within itself during the hardening process. These grains vibrate against each other and resonate at the fundamental frequency of the drum which can be precisely tuned to enhance tonal characteristics.

On the Duggi the Shyahi is offset from the centre of the Maidan. The Tablachee uses this extra exposed Maidan skin to apply pressure with the heel of their hand and bend the Pudi skin to adjust pitch while striking it with their fingers. On the Purra, the Shyahi is in the centre of the Maidan. The pitch of the Purra is tuned to the same note around its circumference by controlling and adjusting the tension of the Badri + Pudi + Shyahi; hence the frequency at which the small particles of the Shyahi vibrate against each other.

Language of the Tabla (*Video Reference - 5:20*)

The Tabla is known as a talking drum. This is based on the language of Tabla and the idea that the Purra and Duggi are having a conversation with each other, the Tablaji, other musicians, and the audience. The language of the Tabla is a syllabic, Bol (Varan)⁸ based musical language passed from Guru (Teacher) to Shishya (Student) through an oral tradition that started getting codified in Vedic literature between 4000 to 1000 BCE.⁹

This language is similar to the modern day concept of Beatboxing. Each Bol (syllable) is a vocal representation of the hand position, finger stroke, & technique used by the player in relation to the Tabla and the resulting sound which is created.

The following Figure shows how the Tabla alphabet and language is structured (*Video Reference - 5:53*)

⁷ David Courtney, *The Syahi* excerpt from *The Tabla Pudi*
<https://chandrakantha.com/tablasite/articles/pudi4.htm>

⁸ David Courtney, *Basic Strokes and Bols* <http://chandrakantha.com/tablasite/bsicbols.htm>

⁹ Ken Hunt, Simon Broughton, Mark Ellingham, James McConnachie, & Orla Duane, *Karnatic Instrumental Music* from *World Music Volume 2: Latin & North America, Caribbean, India, Asia, and Pacific*. Rough Guides Ltd., 2000. p. 79.

Combining Duggi & Purra Bols/sounds/strokes expands the Tabla alphabet and language to create words and phrases. *(Video Reference - 7:10)*

GE + TA = DHA
GA + THIN = DHIN
KE then TE = KIT
KE then TE = KUT
TE then KE = TIK
TE then KE = TAK
TE then TE = TIT
TIT KIT TIK TAK

Combining these Bols in different ways enables one to create phrases & sentences known as Taals or rhythmic cycles as shown in samples below. (*Video Reference - 7:45*)

Samples of RHYTHMIC CYCLES or TAALS

6 Beat Dadra

DHA THIN THIN TAK DHIN DHIN

7 Beat Roopak

THIN THIN TATA DHIN DHADHA DHIN DHADHA

8 Beat Kaherva

DHA THIT THIN THIN TAK THIT DHIN DHIN

16 Beat Rhythmic Cycle

DHA DHIN DHIN DHA DHA DHIN DHIN DHA
DHA THIN THIN TA TA DHIN DHIN DHA

These and other sounds from the Tabla alphabet can further be combined to create compositions of paragraphs, short stories, poetry & prose of varying emotions, complexities, and lengths in the form of Peshkaars, Kaidas, Relas, Uthaans and more. (*Video Reference - 8:36*)

A Tabla student who understands and has built a relationship with this percussive language can then apply the Tabla hand/finger technique or adapt it to perform on other instruments, MIDI controllers, sound objects, and more to create sounds and patterns.

Tuning and other Melodic Properties

Tuning the Purra is a critical first step of the Tabla process and practice. The Tabla is a melodic percussion instrument and the Purra is generally tuned to the root note or tonic of the song the Tabla musician is performing or the musician(s) they are accompanying. Once tuned, the Tablachee then starts to play the Bols, Taals, rhythms, & melodies on the Tabla. (*Video Reference - 9:40*)

Each Purra has an approximate tuning range of about 2-3 tones. However, the instrument maker generally constructs each Purra to sit at its proverbial sweet spot or natural tuning.

This natural tuning is determined based on the size of body, quality of Pudi, and the amount, quality, and application of the Shyahi. For optimum and better life and use; it is advised to keep the Purra at its natural tuning and not adjust too often or unnecessarily.

Tuning the Purra and Duggi is carried out by a hammer. (*Video Reference - 9:45*) Coarse tuning is controlled by adjusting the Gittay (dowels) which are placed between the outer shell of the Purra/Duggi and underneath the Badri. The Gittay are struck down for more tension/higher pitch & up for less tension/lower pitch. The rim or Gajara is struck for fine tuning; down for higher pitch & up for lower pitch.

A Tabla player will sometimes take two, three, or more pre-tuned Purra of different notes to a rehearsal or performance depending on what situation requires. Tuning before/during a performance to the collaborating musician and space is expected within reason, particularly for fine tuning to the lead instrument in relation to the space. Extreme or drastic tuning can distract from the performance atmosphere, at times prove to be a laborious process, and not always successful, especially if the target note is outside the tuning range of the particular Purra. If major tuning is required, it is usually done between pieces or breaks in the performance.

Tabla Tarang (*Video Reference - 9:54*)

Tabla Tarang is the artistic practice of simultaneously creating melodies and rhythms with the Tabla. Usually one Duggi and a certain number of Purra are tuned to specific notes of a song or scale. The Tablachee then plays Tabla Taals, repertoire, and compositions while striking the differently tuned Purra to express melody.

Why TABLIX (*Video Reference - 10:42*)

TABLIX was birthed at a time when all my other forms of communication were moving towards the digital realm. Simultaneously digital technology for ideation, production and performance was becoming increasingly more accessible and ubiquitous in the world of music. The creative goal instigating TABLIX was to digitally pitch shift & compose, edit, perform Digital Tabla Tarang.

My broad experience of learning, playing, collaborating, and performing with the Tabla for over 35 years has informed the philosophy, design, and development of TABLIX. The Tabla, its language of Bols, and the technique used to play those strokes are part of my innate character. This relationship with the Tabla is the foundation upon which I explore music and other instruments and sound objects from around the world.

The Tabla language, artform, performance technique, and ergonomics are at the core of the research and development of TABLIX. These meaningful, creative guides, and parameters helped provide me with a focused decision making approach & strategy throughout the process.

I believe this has resulted in a synergistic integration of the Tabla artform with digital music production technology providing opportunities for the purpose of musical creation, connection, communication & collaboration. This foundation hopefully serves as the starting point of continuing TABLIX conversations through the language of the Tabla with MIDI and the digital realm.

How Does TABLIX Work? (*Video Reference - 18:19*)

TABLIX is an augmented Tabla; the Tabla itself remains as the main performance instrument/interface for the musician. The Duggi (bass drum of Tabla) & Purra (treble drum of Tabla) each have pickups (puD & puP) respectively installed on them. The Duggi also has an internal mic (imD) installed inside its body. These connect to the audio interface (RME Fireface UFX) where the audio signal is converted from an analog to a digital signal which is then sent to the digital audio workstation (DAW) Ableton Live.

Once in Ableton, the puD signal and puP signal are each processed in their separate audio tracks. The imD signal is routed through its own track and then to the puD track inside the DAW so that all software processing for the Duggi is done on one audio track.

TABLIX as a software is a 3 component Max/MSP device hosted in Ableton Live. The Duggi component of the device (D-TABLIX) is hosted on the puD track. The Purra component of the device (P-TABLIX) is hosted on the puP track, and a third Tabla MIDI track (TMDt) hosts the MIDI-TABLIX component of the device.

Other equipment which form the TABLIX interface are:

- In ear noise cancelling monitors for my own personal mix to hear only the processed digitally pitch shifted Tabla and whatever else I want/need in my in ear mix. This helps mitigate the effect of any latency issues arising from TABLIX processing and furthermore prevents me from hearing the acoustic unpitched acoustic Tabla sound.
- I perform standing up and have my Tabla and other components placed on a table. As a result I can make use of my feet while performing. I use a USB MIDI foot pedal

(Keith Macmillan SoftStep) to further alter my desired input or output sound via effects, looping, or MIDI control of other parameters within my DAW.

- Touch based MIDI controller (touchable) used to launch sequences, clips, compose, edit, record, and change parameters within my DAW.

Digital Pitch Shifting (*Video Reference - 14:50*)

The input note for the analog Purra is tuned to C; generally C3, but the exact octave of what the Purra is tuned to is flexible and arbitrary. P-TABLIX is programmed to know that it will be receiving a C tuned Purra. The input note for the Duggi is less critical due to its low frequency, but if/when possible I aim to keep this tuned at C or G.

MIDI note messages are used to convey what the desired output pitch (monophonic) or chord (polyphonic upto 4 voices) should be for Purra. The same is applied to the Duggi in all examples below, but we will focus on the Purra as it is the treble and more tonal drum. For example: if we want the output pitch of the Purra to be F then a MIDI note message of F would be required. If we want the output of the Purra to be the G Major Chord then the MIDI note messages of G,B, & D would be required. The MIDI note messages are hosted on the TMDt and can be sent realtime by the Tabla performing artist themselves or by a collaborating artist. The velocity amount of the MIDI note message(s) does not affect the sound or intensity of the output pitched sound in any way. Therefore the performance dynamics are controlled and expressed through the playing and emotion of the Tablachee as it would be on an acoustic Tabla.

As a solo artist I pre-program the desired output pitch or chord messages in a 1 bar long clip. I launch this clip with the setting for it to be continuously looped until I stop the clip. The MIDI-TABLIX device reads the MIDI note message and communicates the desired output pitch to the P-TABLIX device. The P-TABLIX device calculates and applies the amount of transposition or pitch shifting (chord shifting) required and outputs the digitally pitch shifted Purra (from puP track) and Duggi (from puD track) sounds to the master channel in the DAW. There will be no sound output from the puP track if the TABLIX-P device doesn't receive MIDI note message(s) information from the MIDI-TABLIX component. Similarly there will be no sound output from the puD tracks to the master if there are no MIDI note messages being received by the TABLIX-D device. There will also be no sound, regardless of MIDI note message condition if the Tablachee chooses to mute the acoustic Tabla as part of their standard performance technique.

Digital Tabla Tarang (*Video Reference - 1:00, 16:08, 17:20, & 21:30*)

This is a process and performance technique in which the Tabla-wala can create and express melodies and rhythms simultaneously with TABLIX. The process is the same as described in the digital pitch shifting above however the MIDI note messages are continuous as they would be in a MIDI composed/edited melody or chord progression. It is important that the MIDI note messages of the melody or chord progression are continuous such that there is no break from one note message to the next along the timeline. Any small or large space between subsequent MIDI note messages would cause a break in the signal processing that TABLIX is undertaking and result in an unpleasant sound dropout and digital glitch sounds.

MIDI Connectivity

MIDI connectivity also allows the TABLIX artist to sync MIDI clocks with collaborating musicians to maintain time based effects in a collaborative setting with other electronic or MIDI based musicians. It also provides external control to collaborating musicians (who are also using Ableton Live) for launching clips within the TABLIX Ableton Live session.

Sound

TABLIX provides optimized sound design, mix, control when working live performance or recording sound engineers. In essence the engineer receives a separate left and right XLR and/or ¼" output audio signal or submix as they require direct from TABLIX audio interface.

Logistics

A lighter and smaller setup allows for more efficient and cost effective travelling and touring. The TABLIX setup and teardown is also improved and quite flexible for environments where it is the preferred choice over the conventional Tabla setup.

TABLIX Now and Beyond

TABLIX enables me to expressively imagine, create, and perform in wanted, expected, and unexpected musically evolving ways. As a Tablawala I can still use my familiar, expressive, artistic Tabla technique but TABLIX is undoubtedly a new instrument and interface; and one that I would only use for certain forms of musical expression, collaboration, and performance spaces and spheres.

Over time, I have realized how TABLIX in turn has started informing what I play and how I express my intentions and emotions through sound, music, and technology. This is not entirely different from what happens between musicians and their instruments in other cases where the depth of the relationship becomes the expression as opposed to musician, technique, or instrument alone.

The important factor here is that the onset of my conversation & relationship at the precipice of the digital world, particularly as an analog/acoustic Tabla musician started with an artform and expression that was familiar, deeply meaningful, and synergistic to my being. If these can be considered intrinsically beneficial qualities of beginning a new, honest, engaging and hopefully continuous relationship with technology or otherwise, then creating TABLIX and other musical interfaces in this purposeful manner is in itself a meaningful and rather important exploration for the musician and their respective artform.

As with any conversation or relationship we learn, adapt, incorporate or dismiss ideas, concepts, principles, methods, information, knowledge and more in pursuit to have conversations we can and want to continue. The next phase of the TABLIX conversation I would like to continue with the digital world is leading me down a path to research and develop an expressive hardware or digital instrument/interface that can sound like a natural Tabla if & when the Tablachee prefers or to use it as a MIDI controller to control other sounds and parameters that respond to the natural language and technique of the Tabla.

References

- 1) [ICLI 2020 - Gurpreet Chana TABLIX Presentation](#)
- 2) David Courtney, Dr. T.A. Reddy, Todd Dombrowski, *The Tabla Site*, <http://chandrakantha.com/tablasite/>
- 3) David Courtney, *The Structure and Construction of the Tabla Pudi*, <http://chandrakantha.com/tablasite/articles/pudi.htm>
- 4) David Courtney, *Tabla Making in the Deccan*, <http://chandrakantha.com/tablasite/articles/tblamkng.htm>
- 5) David Courtney, *Basic Strokes and Bols*, <http://chandrakantha.com/tablasite/bsicbols.htm>
- 6) Sadanand Naimpalli, *Theory and Practice of Tabla*. Popular Prakashan, 2006.
- 7) Ken Hunt, Simon Broughton, Mark Ellingham, James McConnachie, & Orla Duane, *Karnatic Instrumental Music from World Music Volume 2: Latin & North America, Caribbean, India, Asia, and Pacific*. Rough Guides Ltd., 2000.
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- 9) MIDI Association <https://www.midi.org/>, <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MIDI>
- 10) [Ableton Live](#)
- 11) [RME Interfaces](#)
- 12) Cycling 74, [Max/MSP](#)

Support Links

- 1) [Red Bull Music](#)
- 2) [Academy - TABLIX demo/talk/performance](#)
- 3) [TABLIX Guthman Music Competition Video](#)
- 4) [Nagma Ishq Live at Koerner Hall](#)
- 5) [Discovery Live at Koerner Hall TABLIX Description 2017.pdf](#)
- 6) More details about [TABLIX](#)
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